

Nigerian Socio-Economic System and The Parable of The Rich Man and Lazarus (Luke 16.19-31): A Comparative Analysis for Nigeria Contemporary Society

Umeokoli, Paul Okechukwu

Department of Religion and Human
Relations, Nnamdi Azikiwe University,
Awka, Anambra State
Revokey2007@yahoo.co.uk

Abstract

The socio-economic system in Nigeria could be likened to social framework of the parable of the rich man and Lazarus (Luke 16.19-31). This is seen from widening gulf between the very few wealthy and numerous citizens living far below the poverty level in Nigeria. That is to say that very few of the citizenry are extremely rich while the huge percentage live in abject poverty. This when compared with the Greco-Roman world would have some common views as regards to poverty, inequality and social interaction. The reason for such situation in the two worlds, Nigeria and the world of the Parable, is not due to lack of resources but the ill use, misallocation and misappropriation of such resources. The focus of this study therefore is to x-ray the socio-economic and socio-political background of the two worlds so as to see a way of finding a solution to the widening gap that exists between the rich and the poor in Nigeria. The principal findings of this study reveal that poverty is still on the increase in Nigeria despite the rich human and material resources in the country with its concomitant effects: hunger, poor education, dehumanization, poor medical care, and the rest. Furthermore, the many economic policies and poverty alleviation programs made to arrest these challenges have not made any significant impression on the huge problem of poverty in Nigeria. The study however recommends the following solutions to reducing poverty in Nigeria and building up a sustainable socio-economic system in the country and they are: organizing skill acquisition programs for self-reliance, creating employment opportunities and provision of interest-free loan to enable the less privileged stand on their feet financially. There is bound likely to be some positive results when these recommendations are implemented.

Key Words: *Parable, Rich man, Comparison, Socio-Economic System, Poor*

Introduction

Poverty with its concomitant effects of alienation, marginalization and dependency poses serious challenge to Nigerian society. The increasing incidence of poverty in Nigeria in spite of various efforts used by a range of poverty-related programs and schemes in the country is really an irony. It is paradoxical in the sense that Nigeria is endowed with great potentials that is capable

of making it a poverty free nation yet a huge number of Nigerians live in poverty level. This leads to a mad rush for wealth as an escape route to poverty and yet many end up poorer and devastated.

The socio-economic system in Nigeria is a *replica* of the social framework of Luke's Gospel: a nation with a widening gulf between very few wealthy and numerous citizens living far below poverty level. Their wealth if equitably distributed will instantly render Nigeria a poverty-free nation. But unfortunately, the majority of Nigerian families fall within the poverty line, while a very tiny percentage is starkly rich. That is to say that the greatest problem of the Lucan world and contemporary Nigeria society is socio-economical and all other problems hang on the above.

Consequently, Luke's concern for social and economic revolution and reformation by his attitudes towards wealth, property, marginalized, poor and social outcasts has been extremely acknowledged by New Testament Scholars and Economists. The parable of the rich man and Lazarus (Luke 16:19-31) in particular, despite significant debates on its several unusual characteristics has attracted the favour of the New Testament scholarship on the themes of wealth and poverty in the New Testament and in the gospel of Luke in particular.

This work will use the study of the parable of the rich man and Lazarus (Luke 16.19-31) to portray the plight of the poor in the hand of some few rich men in the contemporary Nigerian society. The persistent social interaction which always results to ostentatious lifestyle on the side of the rich and abject suffering on the side of the poor should be a serious concern to the society and the church in particular. Poverty is never idealized. It should be alleviated because marginalization and oppression can turn people away from the Lord, but wealth tends to do even more as people think they can independently supply all their own needs thereby act in such a manner that can bring about dehumanization, injustice and oppression.

Background of the Lucan World and Nigerian Socio-economic World

Luke, a physician of Antioch and acclaimed author of St Luke's Gospel carefully presented the parable of the rich man and Lazarus (Luke 16.19-31) in a way of addressing the great physical, economical, ethical, religious and political stress of the Greco-Roman world. It is a world of social status and social stratification; and a world where eschatological anticipation is rampant. A world defined around power and privilege and is measured by a complex of phenomena: a religious purity, family heritage, landownership, vocation, ethnicity, gender, education and age (Kingsbury,

1969). It was into this society that Jesus was born and within this society that He began his public ministry.

Luke presents Jesus as a social reformer who stood to fight the urgent dichotomy between the rich and a large population of the poor who lived little above the hunger line together with its gross exploitation and social injustice. In this case, the poor in Lucan community includes; the sick, beggars, lepers, the outcast, widows and the likes of them. These categories of people rely on the mercies of the rich. The parable of the rich man and Lazarus (Luke 16.19-31) in particular is situated in the above socio-political and socio-economic and socio-religious backgrounds. Probably this harsh economic situation could have affected Lazarus to the extent that he could not even care for his deteriorating health condition.

Luke is a crusader against social injustice and social strata that are prevalent during his time and he stands to fight such social structure that is against the kingdom which Jesus came to establish. That is to say that Luke is trying to protect the interest of the poor. The socio-economic gap that exists in the Lucan community gave rise to the socio-economic conflicts that Luke appears to have striven to settle. His strategy is consolation for the poor and criticism of the rich. Esler (1996) sums it up thus: “There was a widespread oppression of the over-populated mass of the lower classes, high Taxation, natural disasters and societal polarization in the Lucan Greco-Roman world” (p.19). The problem is not simply that very few percentage of the populace has more than enough while many others are hungry, naked and homeless, the depth and reality of the problem is that those who were rich had power over those who were poor. But more importantly, the socio-economic system supports and constantly increases it, so that the rich get deliberately richer while the poor get poorer and have less control of their future. Stambaugh and Balch (1986) further put it thus:

In terms of power, influence, money and the perceptions of the time, we can divide the population of the Roman world into two main categories; those with influence and those without it, the honourable and the humble, those who govern and those who were governed, those who had property and those who did not. The upper category was very small, the lower, very large (p.110).

Such society was marked with exploitation of the poor and ostentation, conspicuous or vulgar display of wealth and success, especially designed to impress people. In such a socio-economically

tough society, unless the wealthy took action to help the poor survive; they might on a daily basis face starvation and even death.

The modern Nigeria society shares a lot of things in common with the above as regards to the social inequality between the rich and the poor with the Lucan Greco-Roman world. However, the situation in Nigeria may be slightly different from that of the Lucan Greco-Roman Palestine. Aside from their differences their shared ideas hinges on the inequality that exists between the rich and the poor citizens. In Nigeria for example the social interaction between the rich and the poor is nothing to write home about. Nigeria is a nation of a widening gulf between very few wealthy and numerous citizens living far below poverty level. The rich people in Nigeria context are prototypes of the rich man in Luke 16:19-31 and they comprise of the following as enumerated by Ottuh (2014):

1. Those who own big companies but pay workers peanuts as salaries.
2. Those who are in the seat of political and economic powers but do not care about how the resources of the nation can be used in such a way that the poor can benefit.
3. Those who increase school fees indiscriminately thereby depriving the poor from attaining education.
4. Those who monopolize all businesses living no room for the poor to gain access to any meaningful business to better their lots.
5. Those who hijacked all enabling environment for business and academic leaving the poor at the periphery.

The problem however is not that few Nigerians are rich and numerous Nigerians poor, but the rich control the affairs or the destinies of the poor populace with little or no interest in the betterment of the poor and their social systems. It is obvious that most of poor people in Nigeria are not really lazy, of course some of them are trying their best to work hard to make ends meet yet they get it very difficult due to lack of enabling environment. However, a summary of the Lucan Greco-Roman world and the modern Nigeria society could be outlined as:

1. They are worlds with great concern for political balance of power.
2. Their eschatological anticipation is rampant because of social and economic stress.
3. Their social status are characterized with social stratification.

4. Their worlds are defined around power and privilege which meant that their belief on social justice and inequality of status and opportunity are based on one's achievements and prestige.
5. The worlds where the rich enjoy a secured maximum welfare; freedom and happiness at the detriment of the poor who are denied of these basic rights.

Interpretation of the Parable of the Rich Man and Lazarus (Luke 16:19-31) in Nigeria Context

Levels of interpretations have been given to the parable of the rich man and Lazarus (Luke 16.19-31). Snodgrass (2008) argues that the parable is an explanation of what is happening in Jesus ministry, the welcome of the poor into God's kingdom which is figuratively represented by Abraham's Bosom. The sinners whose life kept outside the kingdom are now being welcomed into the Kingdom. Other level of interpretation is offered by a very few scholars like Crossan (1980) who takes the parable as the reversal of fortunes that comes with the kingdom advent.

However, the parable can be seen from two perspectives: from the rich man point of view and that of the poor Lazarus, the emphasis being the existing gulf between the two both in this life and in the life to come. The parable of rich man and Lazarus is about money and the implication of the use of money. It is a pointer to the biblical injunction about the use of wealth.

The parable when interpreted in Nigerian context would be understood to mean more than the exchange of money in whatever denomination. Ottuh (2014) interprets it to mean an apologetic against the dehumanization of the poor in the society. It also implies greed and the desire for self-indulgence. An application of this to Nigeria context would represent the country's politicians who have focused mainly on enriching themselves to the detriment of the people who elected them into their offices. They build vast empires for themselves and deprive the people of such basic amenities, like good roads, housing, water and electricity. Okhomiene (1963) describes this act of looting public money for personal gains as madness. He said, "Why will somebody steal the money meant for road construction, building of schools, for hospitals and sadly, such money they will not even finish in five generations" (P.68). He maintains that political office holders in Nigeria should undergo psychiatric test for such unhealthy attitude to life. The Ijaw community in Gbaramatu kingdom, Delta state is a good example of Okhomiene's argument against Nigerian politicians.

Gbaramatu is a community that has over 26 oil wells yet they are living in thatched bamboo houses, no drinking water, no school, health centers and electricity.

The facts above are clear indications that the rich men in the contemporary Nigerian society are like the one in the parable of the rich man and Lazarus. The rich man there represents the successful people who have reached the top. They have no regard for poor and display their self-sufficiency to enjoy material pleasures. The rich are frequently flown abroad for medical check-up without putting into consideration the poor who cannot afford the hospital bill in domestic hospitals how much more abroad. Another point of reference to the parable in Nigerian context is the area of remuneration of workers. Some rich people hardly pay their workers thereby reducing them to untold hardships and as a result, they and their families end up beggars or subject themselves to other menial jobs in order to augment their poor salary. This is a clear example of man's inhumanity to man and an instance is the Nigeria private schools where many of the proprietors of schools collect hundreds of thousands of naira from students and pay their staff peanuts at the end of the month as salary.

The parable from onset made a clear impression about the life of the two figures involved. The rich man has a life, while the poor man does not. The rich man throws away food; the poor man must scrounge for it. The above conditions are typical examples of what happens in Nigeria between the rich and the poor. In the story Lazarus did not speak. His situation is so pathetic that no one would likely hear him if he had spoken. This is what the poor generally suffer. They are hardly heard even in the midst of their suffering. Jesus' teaching in this parable shows that God wants the rich to care for the less-privileged in the society. The rich should not be selfish with their wealth. The parable teaches that the poor should not be abandoned, they should be cared for and their dignity respected.

Government Efforts towards Poverty Alleviation in Nigeria

It is proved that majority of the population in Nigeria is considered to be living in poverty level. Evidences in Nigeria show that the number of those in poverty has continued to increase. Ogwumike, (2001) for example avows that the number of those in poverty increased from 27% in 1980 to 46% in 1985 and to 67% in 1996; by 1999 it increased to more than 70%. Poverty cannot be removed but can at least be alleviated. Consequently, past and present Nigerian governments

have attended to reduce poverty by attempting many poverty alleviation programs aiming at restoring and reconstructing the economy.

Poverty alleviation programs ranging from Operation Feed the Nation of 1978, the Green Revolution of 1982, the Directorate of Foods Roads and Rural Infrastructures DFFRI, the National Directorate for Employment NDE, Poverty Alleviation Programme, PAP up to the National Poverty Eradication Programme, NAPEP were all attempts made by various governments in the country to curb the menace.

The above government's interventions to alleviate poverty in Nigeria have failed to achieve the objectives for which they were established. The failure of the above programs is based on the following reasons:

- a. They were mostly not designed to alleviate poverty but to enrich the initiators.
- b. They lacked clearly defined policy framework with proper guidelines for poverty alleviation.
- c. They suffered from political instability, political interference, policy and macroeconomic dislocations.
- d. They lacked continuity.
- e. Corruption.

These programs only appeared on the pages of newspapers, magazines and News conferences but failed to deliver their objectives (Maduagwu, 2000). The billions of Naira engulfed by the programs proved to be colossally wasteful and rendered the entire populace more miserable than they were. For Nigeria to hope to be a poverty-free country, the leaders must have the eyes that see innumerable 'Lazaruses' (the poor) lying at the gate longing to be fed. There must be a complete change of attitude among the leaders: selfishness, greed and a wanton desire to amass wealth for future generations must never to be found among those considered for the country's leadership positions.

The Way Forward to the Issues of Poverty in Nigeria

Following the failure of the government various efforts and strategies to alleviate poverty in Nigeria, it is expedient to proffer a more lasting solution to the problem. Consequently, the study suggests three solutions to curbing the menace of poverty in Nigeria and they are:

- a. Youth Empowerment
- b. Vocational education
- c. Human and capital development

a. Youth Empowerment

Youth empowerment is identified as one of the major strategies to poverty alleviation in Nigeria. The beneficial outcomes of this strategy are: improved social skills, improved behaviour, increase academic esteem and increased self-efficacy. Youth empowerment encourages young people to take charge of their lives. They do this by addressing their situation and then take it in order to improve their access to resources and transform their consciousness through their beliefs, values and attitudes (Adewale, 2003). There are numerous models that youth empowerment programs use that help youth achieve empowerment. These programs can be through non-profit organizations, government organizations, schools and private organizations.

The study however advocates that if the Nigeria youths are empowered, they can gain momentum to become viable and become institutionalized and, in that way, poverty would be reduced to the barest minimum. It is also believed that the process would create opportunities to learn, practice, and increase skills. It will also develop in them the confidence necessary to become productive and healthy adults. The study goes further to suggest the following interdependent dimensions of which this could be achieved:

1. Psychological empowerment: this enhances individual's consciousness, belief in self-efficiency, awareness and knowledge of problems and solutions to the problems. This dimension of youth empowerment would create self-confidence and give the Nigerian youth skills to acquire knowledge.
2. Community empowerment: This would be made possible when the leaders of various communities especially in Igboland would focus on enhancing and creating a network of support to mobilize their youths towards economic empowerment. This could be achieved through exposure to some entrepreneurial skills so as to be proactive both to themselves and their various communities instead of creating nuisance and state of insecurity to their neighborhoods and consequently multiplying poverty in the society.

This study therefore calls upon the local, state and federal governments of Nigeria, the Church and non-profit based organizations to provide programs centred on youth empowerment. When the

youths participate in established empowerment programs, they see a variety of benefits. This is also one of the ways to apply the message of the parable to accelerate the plights of the poor in the country.

b. Vocational Education: A Tool for Poverty Alleviation in Nigeria

Vocational Education is really a tool for poverty alleviation in Nigeria. Technical and vocational education and training is another way and most effective human resource development strategies that Nigerian government, the Church and other non- government agencies should embrace so as to train and modernize the technical work force for industrialization and national development. Vocational education and training are essential parts of development for many nations to grow economically. Most Nigerian youths have, before now, been of the idea that traditional four-five year university degree is the only essential tool needed for self-empowerment. That idea is gradually been addressed, as more and most post-secondary students and even graduates seek to embrace vocational education and skill acquisition as the key to deal with unemployment and unholy dependence on white collar job.

Vocational education is an important part of education system in Australia, Germany, Leicester and Switzerland and one element of German model. In most developed countries, the government is often between the gaps to support the vocational education in training institutions. In Nigeria, the case is been quite different for a while now. Vocational skill centres are poorly funded which has resulted in poor quality training facilities and trainers (except for privately run vocational schools). However, with the current reform in education sector, it is hoped that the federal government sustains its current interest on reviving vocational education. In the News from the national online-ng on 27th February, 2019, the federal government of Nigeria is said to have retracted long un-kept commitment to providing vocational education through skill acquisition and development programs. Such mindset towards vocational training only makes this form of education appear as a fall-back than a healthy choice, and does not encourage its acceptance nonetheless. Gone are the days when technical education should be regarded as reserve for drop-outs, low performing or financially deficient students. There are good numbers of people with vocational education earning a lot more than the four-five year degree holders and making a good career progress.

Therefore, in order for technical and vocational education to effectively contribute to industrialization, economic growth, wealth creation and poverty eradication in Nigeria; particularly in Igboland, wealth creation and skills training must be of high quality and competency-based and be made available mostly for poor and vulnerable members of the society as part of the poverty alleviation programs.

c. Raising Human Capital Development

The term human capital was invented by economist, Theodore Schultz in the year 1960 to reflect the value of human capacities. He believed that human capital was like any other type of capital which could be invested through education, training and enhanced benefits that will lead to an improvement in the quality and level of production. Nigeria is blessed with a pool of human resources but has not been able to harness this great potential especially towards eradicating poverty in the country. Though there have been previous attempts that have failed to yield a positive result. This study however suggests that more effort should be made in this area but this time not the government alone. Other agencies including the Church should invest in human capital accumulation through education, training and skill acquisition.

The government non-chalant attitude to both human and capital development in Nigeria has discouraged most small-scale businesses in the country and this have added to the problem of poverty and unemployment in the country. The geographical location of some places, bad road network and communication problem have left the people living in those areas inaccessibility and unable to distribute their products for sales hence causing them into unavoidable hardship just to earn a living.

Conclusion

All we have gathered from this study confirms that the traditional teaching of the parable of the rich man and Lazarus (Luke 16.91-31) is the right attitude to wealth; concern for social justice and care for the poor, the needy and marginalized. It is all about the attitudes and actions concerning wealth and poverty. The social stratification which forms the framework of the parable shows Luke's deep concern for the socio-economic systems of his community with its social polarization between the rich and the poor. This is equally the same with Nigeria contemporary

society. In a way to bridge the gap it is expected that the Church, the government and non-governmental bodies should join hands to ameliorate the plight of the poor masses especially in Nigeria.

Recommendations

1. The Church should intensify her caring ministry. A more viable charity ministry should be operated by the church to care for the immediate hunger of the poor before and during their empowerment process. For those who are irredeemably incapacitated, the church should see it as a point of duty to feed them in case they are abandoned by their families.
2. The government should as a matter of all seriousness make policies that will check mate the ostentatious living and expenditure especially during ceremonies like burial and marriage which directly or indirectly push the poor into unnecessary expenditure in the name of meeting up with the social demand which has been established by the rich.
3. The government should endeavour to formulate policies that will better the plights of the poor.
4. In general, the church, government and non-governmental agencies should help to create more employment opportunities and provision of interest-free loan to enable the less privileged stand on their feet financially
5. Youth empowerment, vocational, skill acquisition and human capital development should be emphasized.

References

- Crossan, U.C. (2008). *Nigerian democracy: An x-ray*. Mineapolis: Bethany.
- Esler, P. F. (1996). *Community and gospel in Luke-Acts: The social and political motivations of Lucan theology*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Hussani, E. O. (2014). *The theological implications of the parable of the rich man and Lazarus*. Ibadan: SCM.
- Kingsbury J. D. (1969). *The parables of Jesus in Matthew 13: A study in redaction-criticism*. Richmond: John Knox.

Maduagwu, A. (2000). *Alleviating Poverty in Nigeria*. Retrieve Online from <http://www.afbis.com/analysis/alleviating-poverty.htm> on 9 September,2000.

Ogwumike, S.M. (2005). *Towards a better Nigeria*. New Jersey: Eagle woods.

Okhomine, k. (1963). *Government Approach towards a meliorating poverty in Nigeria*. New York: Crune & Stratton.

Ottuh, J. A. (2014). *The story of Lazarus and the rich Man (Luke 16:19-31): Retold in a Nigerian context*. *Global Journal of Arts Humanities and Social Sciences* 2.3, 59-76.